

Studies on the Complexes of Some Triphenyl Methane Dyes with Chromium, Molybdenum and Tungsten

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Crystal violet, malachite green and fuchsine react with potassium chromate, sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate in 1N H₂SO₄ to give 1:1 metal ligand complexes. However, in the case of chromate only an addition product with these cationic dyes is obtained. Infra red spectra of the isolated complexes show that the dyes are bound to the metal through the nitrogen atom.

TRIPHENYL methane (TPM) dyes have been used in potentiometric titrations¹ and in spot test analysis². Recently we had used these dyes for the spectrophotometric³ estimation of Ce(IV) and also studied the nature of the complexes⁴ formed by them with Ce(IV). These studies have now been extended to the complexes of triphenyl methane dyes with chromium, molybdenum and tungsten.

Experimental

Materials used

Potassium chromate, sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate were AnalaR grade (B D H) reagents. Their solutions were prepared in double distilled water and their strengths determined by the usual methods⁵.

Crystal violet, malachite green and fuchsine dyes were B D H products and were purified by recrystallisation from 50% alcohol before use. Their purity was tested by thin layer chromatography and were found to give a single spot.

Equipment

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out on Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 spectrophotometer using 10 mm glass tubes. Polarographic studies were carried out at 25°C with a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a Fischer capillary. The capillary characteristic was 3.75 mg^{2/3} S^{-1/2}. The solutions were deaerated by bubbling pure nitrogen gas for 10 minutes in an H type cell.

Infrared spectra were recorded on Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Magnetic measurements were carried out by Gouy's method at room temperature.

Isolation of the Complexes

100 ml of 0.1M sodium molybdate, sodium tungstate or potassium chromate in 1N H₂SO₄ was

mixed with 100 ml of 0.1M TPM dye in 1N H₂SO₄ and the solution shaken vigorously for a few minutes. After 15 minutes, the complex got precipitated. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with some 1N H₂SO₄ water, then alcohol and finally with ether. It was dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Analysis of the complexes.

The complex was fused with fusion mixture and the fused mass extracted with water. The extract was boiled for about 5 minutes and heated to dryness on a low flame. The residue was extracted with dilute NaOH in the case of molybdenum and tungsten and with dil HCl in the case of chromium complexes. Molybdenum and tungsten were then estimated as their oxides⁶ while chromium was estimated with potassium ferrocyanide⁶ after reducing to chromium(III) with H₂O₂. SO₄²⁻ in the extracts of Mo and W was estimated as BaSO₄. Nitrogen and carbon content of the complexes were obtained through the kind courtesy of the micro-analytical laboratories, I I P, Dehradun (India).

Results and Discussion

Crystal violet, malachite green and fuchsine form 1:1 soluble complexes with potassium chromate, sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate in 1N H₂SO₄ in the concentration range of 10⁻³M. At higher concentrations (0.1M) of the metal and dyes the complexes separate out as precipitates. The solutions of the complexes show new regions of absorption in the visible region as listed in Table I. A 1:1 stoichiometry for these complexes was found by continuous variation, molar ratio and polarographic methods. Spectrophotometry could not be employed for molybdenum complexes as they give very light colour in dilute solutions.

In increasing concentration of the dyes, the polarographic E_{1/2} of the reversible waves show a shift towards more negative potentials, giving a linear E_{1/2} versus log C plot, whose slope, Δ(E_{1/2})/ΔC

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TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS, ABSORPTION MAXIMA POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THE T P M DYE COMPLEXES

Complex	% Metal	% Carbon	% Nitrogen	% Hydrogen	% Sulphate	Colour	Absorption maxima λ_{nm}	$\Delta(E_{1/2})_c$ $\Delta \log C$	Stability constant (from polarography) $\log K$.
$C_{25}H_{36}N_2HCrO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ Crystal violet	Calc 9.9 Found 10.3	57.1 57.0	8.0 8.2	6.6 6.3	—	Brownish	455	—	—
$C_{25}H_{36}N_2HCrO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ Malachite green	Calc 10.7 Found 10.9	57.2 57.9	5.8 5.8	6.2 5.8	—	Brownish	455	—	—
$C_{20}H_{20}N_2HCrO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ Fuchsine	Calc 11.4 Found 11.1	52.7 52.3	9.2 9.0	5.5 5.5	—	Brownish	440	—	—
$MoO_2(CV)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 13.6 Found 13.7	42.6 42.3	5.9 5.4	5.3 5.1	13.6 13.3	Greenish	—	0.05	3.46
$MoO_2(MG)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 14.5 Found 14.1	41.8 42.0	4.2 4.2	5.0 4.9	14.5 13.9	Greenish	—	0.05	4.02
$MoO_2(FU)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 15.1 Found 14.8	37.8 37.5	6.6 6.0	4.4 4.5	15.1 15.0	Light Violet	—	0.05	3.70
$WO_2(CV)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 23.2 Found 22.9	37.8 37.3	5.3 5.0	4.8 4.4	12.1 11.8	Green	630	0.05	2.50
$WO_2(MG)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 24.5 Found 24.2	36.9 36.8	3.7 3.6	4.4 4.2	12.8 12.6	Green	630	0.05	3.8
$WO_2(FU)SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Calc 25.4 Found 25.5	32.2 33.5	5.8 5.8	3.8 3.7	13.3 12.8	Violet	575	0.08	4.1

CV = Crystal violet

MG = Malachite green

Fu = Fuchsine

TABLE 2—INFRA RED SPECTRAL DATA (CM⁻¹) OF THE TPM DYE COMPLEXES

CV	Complex of CV with			MG	Complex of MG with			FU	Complex of FU with			Assignment
	Cr	Mo	W		Cr	Mo	W		Cr	Mo	W	
—	3400	3400	3400	—	3400	3400	3400	—	3400	3400	3400	ν(H ₂ O) ν(NH ₂)
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	3300	3300	3200	3200	
2840	2840	—	—	2840	2840	—	—	—	—	—	—	N(CH ₃) ₂
2800	2800	—	—	2800	2800	—	—	—	—	—	—	
—	1580	1600	1610	—	1600	1600	1600	—	1600	1620	1620	H ₂ O
1350	1350	1340	1340	1350	1350	1340	1340	—	—	—	—	ν(C-N) of C-N(CH ₃) ₂ ν(C-N) of C-NH ₂
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1260	1260	1180	1180	
—	—	1100	1100	—	—	1100	1120	—	—	1130	1110	ν(SO ₄ ²⁻) W=O, MO=O
—	—	980	960	—	—	960	970	—	—	950	950	
—	900	—	—	—	910	—	—	—	850	—	—	CrO ₄ ²⁻
—	—	340	800	—	—	800	800	—	—	800	800	(H ₂ O) Coordinated
—	—	640	650	—	—	640	620	—	—	620	640	
—	—	580	580	—	—	570	575	—	—	570	580	ν(N-N)

$\log C$, gave the value of p , the complexing number, by Lingane's method⁷ for reversible waves. The value of p was found to be one in all the cases (Table 1) showing the formation of 1:1 complexes (Log analysis showed the value of n to be 1)

In 1N H₂SO₄, MoO₂²⁺ and WO₂²⁺ species exist⁸ and their complexes can be formulated as MoO₂ (T.P.M. dye) SO₄ · 4H₂O and WO₂ (T.P.M. dye) SO₄ · 4H₂O while for chromium, the anion CrO₄²⁻ in the stable species an addition product [T.P.M. dye. HCrO₄] · 2H₂O is formed (Analysis Table 1).

The important infra-red spectral characteristics of the complexes and the dyes are given in table 2. All the complexes show a broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ and around 1600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to water. The complexes of molybdenum and tungsten also show bands around 850 cm⁻¹ and 650 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the rocking and M-O stretching of co-ordinated water⁹ where as the chromium compounds contain no co-ordinated water. The appearance of bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ and around 1600 cm⁻¹ indicates that water may be only weakly co-ordinated in these complexes (strong aquo complex-

ation lowers the H_2O frequency¹¹ by 300 cm^{-1} and raises the bending frequency by some tens of cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra also shows a sharp band of medium intensity around 950 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\text{W}=\text{O}$ and $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ in the complexes of tungsten and molybdenum¹⁰. The complexes of chromium show bands characteristic of CrO_4^{2-} in the 900 cm^{-1} region⁹. The presence of SO_4^{2-} in the complexes of molybdenum and tungsten is also confirmed by the band appearing around 1100 cm^{-1} . The coordination of the dye takes place through nitrogen and is evidenced by the appearance of the metal-nitrogen stretching band in the $580\text{-}570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region for molybdenum and tungsten complexes. This band is absent in the case of chromium complexes, suggesting that an addition product through ionic interaction may be present. The shift in C-N stretching of C-N $(\text{CH}_3)_2$ grouping (appearing at 1350 cm^{-1} in M G and C V) in the complexes of malachite green and crystal violet and C-N stretching of C-NH₂ group in fuchsine complex (appearing at 1200 cm^{-1} in the fuchsine dye) shows co-ordination of the dye through nitrogen⁴ of this group. The $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group in malachite green and crystal violet shows two bands around 2800 cm^{-1} which disappear on coordination through nitrogen with the metal¹¹. The asymmetric NH₂ stretching shows shifts from around 3300 cm^{-1} to around 3200 cm^{-1} in the case of fuchsine, which confirms co-ordination of fuchsine through nitrogen of the NH₂ group. In the case of chromium compounds neither the C-N stretching (in 1300 cm^{-1} region) of the dye shows shifts nor the $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ bands around 2800 cm^{-1} disappear showing thereby that only an addition product is formed.

These dyes act as bidentate ligands⁴. In crystal violet all the three N $(\text{CH}_3)_2$ groups are equivalent and hence any two such groups can enter into co-ordination while in fuchsine the co-ordination appears to be through the two NH₂ groups attached to the phenyl rings which do not carry the $-\text{CH}_3$ group. Magnetic measurements shows the complexes to be diamagnetic as expected.

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